

Amino group immobilized on polyvinyl alcohol as a reusable catalyst for highly accelerated *N*-formylation of amines using formic acid under solvent-free condition

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Abstract : Amino group immobilized on polyvinyl alcohol catalyzed, rapid, chemoselective and practical *N*-formylation of amines using formic acid under solvent-free conditions. The catalyst was found to be compatible with different functional groups and the *N*-formylation proceeded smoothly with amines bearing electron withdrawing as well as electron donating substituents. The process is remarkably simple and environmentally benign. The catalyst can be easily recovered and reused at least four times without any decrease in its high catalytic activity.

Keywords : “Solventless” *N*-formylation, formic acid, amine, polyvinyl alcohol (PVA).

Introduction

Formyl group as an useful and versatile amino-protecting group in peptide synthesis¹. In addition, formamides serve as useful intermediates in the synthesis of medicinally important heterocycles such as substituted aryl imidazoles², 1,2-dihydroquinolines³, oxazolidinones⁴, cancer chemotherapeutic compounds⁵ and as reagents for Vilsmeier formylation⁶, synthesis of formamidines⁷ and isocyanides⁸. Due to Lewis basicity of formamides they could be applied as catalysts in allylation⁹ and hydrosilylation of carbonyl compounds¹⁰. Furthermore, asymmetric allylation of aldehydes has been achieved with chiral formamides¹¹.

Numerous methods of formylation are reported in the literature. Acetic formic anhydride^{12,13}, chloral¹⁴, activated formic acid using DCC¹⁵, EDCI¹⁶, activated formic acid esters¹⁷⁻²⁰, KF-Al₂O₃²¹, ammonium formate²², 2,2,2-trifluoroethyl formate²³, formic acid in combination with sodium formate²⁴, ZnCl₂²⁵, sulfated titania²⁶, Amberlite IR 120²⁷, indium metal²⁸, iodine²⁹, ZnO³⁰ have been used for this purpose. Polyethylene glycol medium³¹, as well as solid supported reagents³² such as silica supported perchloric acid³³, sulfonic acid supported hydroxyapatite encapsulated γ -Fe₂O₃³⁴, sulfated tungstate³⁵ have been also utilised. However, some of these methods are limited only to aromatic primary amines, some others use

expensive toxic organic solvent, toxic, expensive reagents. Also, most of *N*-formylation methods involve rather complicated preparation of catalysts, long reaction time, high temperature and formation of side products. Therefore, development of low-cost, eco-friendly and recyclable catalytic method is of current interest^{36,37}. Herein, we report a solventless method for the *N*-formylation of amines based on treatment with formic acid in the presence of PVA-NH₂.

Results and discussion

For initial optimization experiments, aniline was subjected to a set of reaction conditions. *N*-Formylation of aniline in the absence of any catalyst and solvent at room temperature was rather sluggish (Table 1, entry 1). At room temperature, the presence of PVA has no influence on the rate of *N*-formylation reaction, whereas PVA-NH₂³⁸ caused acceleration to some extent (Table 1, entries 2, 3). In order to study the effect of temperature, all reactions were carried out at 40 °C (Table 1, entries 4-6). It was observed PVA-NH₂ delivered improved results under this condition. Next the catalyst loading was optimised (Table 2, entries 9-11). *N*-Formylation reaction of aniline in the presence of 2.7 mol% of catalyst gave the best yield of the desired product. Notably, the presence of solvent decreased the reaction rate (Table 1, entries 12-14).

The scope and limitations of the optimized reaction

Table 1. Optimization experiments for formylation of aniline

Entry	Molar ratio Aniline/HCO ₂ H	Catalyst	Cat (mol%)	Solvent	Temp. (°C)	Time (h/min)	Yield (%)
1	1/1	–	–	–	rt	5 h	90
2	1/1	PVA	5.4	–	rt	5 h	90
3	1/1	PVA-NH ₂	5.4	–	rt	3.5 h	95
4	1/1	–	–	–	40	2.5 h	95
5	1/1	PVA	5.4	–	40	3 h	95
6	1/1	PVA-NH ₂	5.4	–	40	15 min	95
7	1/2	PVA-NH ₂	5.4	–	rt	1.5 h	95
8	1/2	PVA-NH ₂	5.4	–	40	10 min	95
9	1/2	PVA-NH ₂	2.7	–	40	10 min	95
10	1/1	PVA-NH ₂	2.7	–	40	10 min	95
11	1/1	PVA-NH ₂	1.3	–	40	30 min	95
12	1/1	PVA-NH ₂	2.7	CH ₂ Cl ₂	40	2 h	95
13	1/1	PVA-NH ₂	2.7	CH ₃ CN	40	5 h	95
14	1/1	PVA-NH ₂	2.7	MeOH	40	1 h/18 h	80/80

condition for *N*-formylation of various amines were evaluated. The results are presented in Table 2. *N*-Formylation of substituted anilines rapidly and efficiently irrespective of the substituents (Table 2, entries 1–12). Formylation of anilines containing electron-donating substituents such as CH₃, CH₂CH₃, OCH₃, were relatively fast than anilines with electron-withdrawing groups such as halogen and NO₂. *N*-Formylation of amines was chemoselective in bifunctional compounds containing OH/CONH₂ groups (entries 13–14 and 20). This protocol was also successfully applied to primary and secondary aliphatic amines

Table 2. PVA-NH₂ catalyzed *N*-formylation of amines

Entry	Substrate	Product	Time (min, h)	Isolated yield (%)
1		10 min	95	
2		5 min	97	
3		5 min	98	
4		30 min	95	
5		5 min	95	
6		30 min	92	
7		90 min	98	

Table-2 (contd.)

Table-2 (contd.)

8		10 min	98						
9		Immediately	98						
10		Immediately	98						
11		10 min	95						
12 ^a		5 min	98						
13		10 min	95						
14 ^a		3 h	94						
15 ^a		3 h/4 h	80/96						
16		20 min	97						
					26 ^a		30 min	98	
					27		No reaction	12 h	0
					28		No reaction	12 h	0
					29		No reaction	12 h	0

^aMolar ratio of amine/formic acid : 1/3 was used.

(Table 2, entries 16–22). Secondary aromatic amines were good substrates for the reaction but because of steric effects, *N*-formylation was rather slow (Table 2, entries 23–24). The PVA-NH₂ catalyzed *N*-formylation strategy was studied for *N*-formylation of some selected heteroaromatic amines which provided the desired prod-

ucts in excellent yields (Table 2, entries 25–26). *O*-Formylation of carboxylic acid, alcohol and phenol derivatives under these reaction conditions was not successful (Table 2, entries 27–29).

A tentative mechanism of the reaction is dedicated in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Catalyst re-usability was assessed in the *N*-formylation of aniline. To this end, the reaction was stopped after 10 min (i.e. at 100% conversion) and the catalyst removed by filtration and washed with methanol several times. Table 3 shows the results obtained after four re-use cycles. As can be seen, no significant loss of activity of the catalyst was observed.

Table 3. *N*-Formylation of aniline in the presence of reused PVA-NH₂

Entry	Time (min)	Temperature (°C)	Conversion (%)
1	10	40	100
2	10	40	100
3	10	40	98
4	10	40	95

Conclusion

A basic catalyst consisting of PVA-supported ethanolamine proved highly efficient in the *N*-formylation of aromatic and aliphatic amines. The reagents used are inexpensive and neither inert atmosphere nor dry solvent are required for the success of the reaction. Moreover, the catalyst is stable, non-hygroscopic and resistant to air and heat. The reaction work-up and purification of the products is straightforward and provides the corresponding *N*-formylated amine in excellent yields. The catalyst was re-used at least four times with no appreciable loss of reactivity.

Experimental

The products were purified by column chromatography. The purity determinations of the products were accomplished by TLC on silica gel polygram STL G/UV 254 plates. The melting points of products were determined with an Electrothermal Type 9100 melting point apparatus. The FT-IR spectra were recorded on an Avatar 370 FT-IR Thermo Nicolet spectrometer. The NMR spectra were provided on Bruker Avance 400 MHz instruments in CDCl₃. Elemental analyses were performed using a Costech 4010 CHNS Elemental Analyzer instrument. Mass spectra were recorded with a Varian-MAT spectrometer model CH7A at 70 eV; in *m/z* (rel. %). Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential thermogravimetric (DTG) were performed on a Shimadzu Thermogravimetric Analyzer (TG-50) under air atmos-

phere. All of the products were known compounds and characterized by the IR and comparison of their melting points with known compounds. The structure of selected products was further confirmed by ¹H NMR spectroscopy and mass spectrometry.

Preparation of PVA-NH₂³⁸ :

Ethanolamine (10 mL) was added directly to commercially available polyvinyl alcohol with average molecular weight of 72000 Da (0.5 g) at 80 °C. After 18 h magnetically stirring, methanol (40 mL) was added to the reaction mixture. The solid was filtered off, washed with methanol (5 × 50). The pale yellow precipitate was refluxed with methanol (100 mL) for 18 h. The hot mixture was filtrated and dried in a stove at 50 °C for 24 h.

Characterization of PVA-NH₂ :

FT-IR spectroscopy :

The catalyst structure was defined by FT-IR spectroscopy. Fig. 1 illustrates the FT-IR spectra of the PVA and PVA-NH₂. The peaks at 3549 and 3338 cm⁻¹ due to N-H stretching of immobilized NH₂ on polyvinyl alcohol. In the low frequency region, the presence of the weak N-H bending vibration at 1668 cm⁻¹ confirms the incorporation of amino groups. The peak of the C-N stretching vibration is normally observed in the range of 1250–1020 cm⁻¹.

Fig 1. FT-IR spectra of PVA and PVA-NH₂.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) :

Thermogravimetric studies of pure PVA and PVA-NH₂ at heating rate 10 °C /min was appeared in Fig. 2.

Fig 2. TGA /DTG thermograms of PVA.

It can be seen that both PVA and PVA-NH₂ exhibited a three-step degradation patterns. As PVA contain a small quantity of physically adsorbed water, the first stage of degradation represents the loss of physically adsorbed water, splitting or volatilization of small molecule and/or monomers (weight loss 4.6%, from 21–180 °C). On the other hand above 120 °C elimination of water could be resulted formation of C–C double bond, which consequently leads to formation of polyene. The second stage (weight loss 54.5%, from 181–305 °C) corresponds to side chain decomposition. The higher value of weight loss in second stage was attributed to chemical degradation of some C–C bonds of polymer backbone. In the third stage (weight loss 36.3%, 306–474 °C) the complete decomposition of the main chain of polymer was occurred^{39,40}.

Similarly, TGA/DTG thermo grams of PVA-NH₂ exhibited three distinct weight loss stages. As can be seen, every stage of weight loss was occurred in higher temperature than PVA, this confirmed the modification of the PVA by chemical introduction of ethanolamine, which raised the thermal stability of polymer. The first step (weight loss 3.7%, 25–228 °C) attributed to evaporation of moisture, methanol, ethanolamine and easily degraded components. The mentioned components are strongly bonded to polymer backbone via hydrogen bonding with immobilized NH₂ group on polymer chain. Water elimination was also occurred at higher temperature than PVA. The major mass loss took place in the second step (weight loss 57.3%, 229–442 °C) and was followed by a further mass loss in the third step (34.9%, 443–605 °C). The second stage represents chemical degradation of side chain (C–C side chain bond and amino ethyl group). The third

step of weight loss was predominantly the characteristic degradation of polymer structure (breaking down and cracking of polymer backbone).

Fig 3. TGA/DTG Thermograms of PVA-NH₂.

The results of thermogravimetric analysis are in good agreement with those of the chemical elemental analyses, revealing that 0.271 mmol of ethanolamine was incorporated into the 1.000 g of PVA-NH₂ framework.

Typical procedure for N-formylation of aniline :

Aniline (0.093 g, 1 mmol) and PVA-NH₂ (0.100 g) were mixed thoroughly and treated with formic acid (0.046 g, 1 mmol) in an oil bath at 40 °C. The progress of reaction was monitored by TLC using *n*-hexane/ethyl acetate (1 : 1) as the solvent. After completion of the reaction the reaction mixture was allowed to cool, eluted with ethyl acetate, filtered and neutralized with saturated NaHCO₃ (5 ml). The organic layer was dried over Na₂SO₄. After removal of the solvent under reduced pressure the crude product was recrystallized from Et₂O obtaining 0.114 g crystals (95% yield).

N-Phenylformamide (1) : Yield 95%; m.p. 47–48 °C (Lit. 46–48 °C)⁴¹; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3267 (NH), 3133, 3058, 2982, 2874, 2778, 1691 (C=O), 1600, 1544, 1494, 1441, 1402, 1312, 1254, 1147, 1025, 902, 861, 753, 692, 654, 516 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 121 [M]⁺ (100).

N-(4-Ethylphenyl)formamide (2) : Yield 97%; m.p. 43–44 °C (Lit. 42.5–44 °C)⁴²; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3195 (NH), 3115, 3043, 2964, 2920, 2865, 2761, 1685 (C=O), 1608, 1517, 1453, 1387, 1292, 1216, 1181, 1116, 1026, 963, 819, 762, 597, 541, 479 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 149 [M]⁺ (100).

N-p-Tolylformamide (3) : Yield 98%; m.p. 49–51 °C (Lit. 49–52 °C)⁴³; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3191 (NH), 3105, 3033, 2918, 2869, 2774, 1695 (C=O), 1608, 1518, 1486, 1409, 1396, 1305, 1217, 1113, 1040, 937, 884, 814, 775, 707, 639, 597, 521, 473, 415 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 135 [M]⁺ (80).

N-o-Tolylformamide (4) : Yield 95%; m.p. 58–59 °C (Lit. 58–59 °C)⁴⁴; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3250 (NH), 3207, 3046, 2876, 2782, 1686 (C=O), 1589, 1551, 1505, 1457, 1398, 1285, 1161, 1041, 886, 753, 642, 545, 450 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 135 [M]⁺ (22).

N-(4-Methoxyphenyl)formamide (5) : Yield 95%; m.p. 60–62 °C (Lit. 62–64 °C)⁴⁵; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3245 (NH), 3191, 3128, 3049, 3000, 2968, 2937, 2893, 2837, 2779, 1677 (C=O), 1655, 1606, 1551, 1510, 1458, 1414, 1395, 1304, 1236, 1179, 1153, 1108, 1028, 874, 834, 807, 782, 694, 537, 516, 442, 413 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 151 [M]⁺ (79), 152 [M+1]⁺ (23).

N-(2-Methoxyphenyl)formamide (6) : Yield 92%; m.p. 79–80 °C (Lit. 80–81 °C)⁴⁶; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3253 (NH), 3190, 3129, 3044, 3006, 2961, 2917, 2877, 2833, 1694 (C=O), 1660, 1597, 1535, 1486, 1460, 1430, 1394, 1331, 1286, 1257, 1225, 1181, 1155, 1108, 1047, 1028, 922, 864, 813, 744, 724, 580, 506, 483, 449 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 151 [M]⁺ (98).

N-(4-Bromophenyl)formamide (7) : Yield 98%; m.p. 115–117 °C (Lit. 115–119 °C)⁴¹; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3284 (NH), 3257, 3184, 3113, 3050, 2871, 2771, 1669 (C=O), 1599, 1586, 1535, 1485, 1394, 1306, 1249, 1066, 1005, 878, 821, 772, 751, 514, 407 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 198 [M-2]⁺ (100), 200 [M]⁺ (100), 201 [M+1]⁺ (12).

N-(4-Chlorophenyl)formamide (8) : Yield 95%; m.p. 98–100 °C (Lit. 99–100 °C)⁴³; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3295 (NH), 3260, 3192, 3120, 3059, 2998, 2893, 2790, 1686 (C=O), 1608, 1543, 1490, 1454, 1407, 1397, 1310, 1291, 1252, 1170, 1150, 1106, 1086, 1010, 932, 871, 836, 782, 767, 609, 517, 403 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 155 [M]⁺ (31), 157 [M+2]⁺ (7).

N-(2-Chlorophenyl)formamide (9) : Yield 95%; m.p. 77–78 °C (Lit. 76–80 °C)⁴⁷; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3251 (NH), 3115, 3042, 2990, 2901, 1670 (C=O), 1601, 1544, 1441, 1398, 1300, 1163, 1127, 1035, 939, 863, 739, 674, 537, 442 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 155 [M]⁺ (86), 157

[M+2]⁺ (15).

N-(4-Fluorophenyl)formamide (10) : Yield 96%; m.p. 63–65 °C (Lit. 63–65 °C)⁴⁸; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3179 (NH), 3077, 2983, 2941, 2867, 2778, 1649 (C=O), 1605, 1521, 1485, 1411, 1328, 1287, 1240, 1090, 1037, 830, 803, 755, 601, 520, 469 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 139 [M]⁺ (25).

N-(3-Fluorophenyl)formamide (11) : Yield 95%; m.p. 63–64 °C (Lit. 63–64 °C)⁵; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3279 (NH), 3223, 3166, 3091, 3051, 3007, 2884, 2831, 2786, 2708, 1693 (C=O), 1608, 1556, 1452, 1401, 1339, 1319, 1262, 1151, 1128, 1067, 996, 890, 817, 797, 693, 654, 504, 416 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 139 [M]⁺ (35), 141 [M+2]⁺ (71).

N-(4-Nitrophenyl)formamide (12) : Yield 95%; m.p. 194–196 °C (Lit. 194–196 °C)⁴⁴; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3263 (NH), 3215, 3086, 3047, 3018, 2888, 1688 (C=O), 1621, 1564, 1503, 1413, 1335, 1301, 1269, 1155, 1111, 853, 828, 752, 690, 538 cm⁻¹.

N-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)formamide (13) : Yield 95%; m.p. 134–137 °C (Lit. 135–137 °C)⁴¹; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3321 (OH), 3190 (NH), 3101, 2888, 2802, 2671, 2614, 1673 (CO), 1566, 1513, 1400, 1317, 1253, 1167, 1106, 871, 828, 787, 709, 641, 529, 458, 431 cm⁻¹.

2-Formamidobenzoic acid (14) : Yield 92%; m.p. 168–169 °C (Lit. 167–169 °C)³³; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3436 (OH), 3209 (NH), 3068, 2923, 1686 (C=O carboxyl), 1611 (C=O formyl), 1590, 1507, 1442, 1388, 1291, 1157, 1043, 873, 848, 756, 702, 662, 642, 521, 485, 411 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 164 [M-1]⁺ (24).

2-Formamidobenzamide (15) : Yield 90%; m.p. 118–120 °C (Lit. 119–122 °C)⁴⁹; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3378, 3207 (NH), 3096, 2892, 2802, 1704, 1629 (C=O), 1529, 1453, 1394, 1304, 1172, 1109, 1068, 866, 811, 750, 638, 538, 508 cm⁻¹.

N-Benzylformamide (16) : Yield 98%; m.p. 62–64 °C (Lit. 63–64 °C)⁵⁰; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3292 (NH), 3061, 3029, 1642 (C=O), 1568, 1495, 1451, 1384, 1338, 1300, 1141, 1073, 1037, 813, 738, 695, 628, 604, 574, 473, 463 cm⁻¹; EIMS *m/z* (rel. int.) : 135 [M]⁺ (4).

*N-[(2-Methoxyphenyl)methyl]formamide (17)*⁵¹ : Yield 98%; m.p. 86–90 °C; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3200–2500 (NH), 2996, 2936, 2855, 2775, 2683, 1652 (C=O), 1576, 1500,

1461, 1371, 1333, 1252, 1169, 1111, 1034, 1012, 935, 773, 745, 693, 583, 433 cm^{-1} ; EIMS m/z (rel. int.) : 167 $[\text{M}+2]^+$ (3), 165 $[\text{M}]^+$ (2.5).

N-Cyclohexylformamide (**18**) : Yield 98%; m.p. 30–31 °C (Lit. 30–31 °C)⁵²; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3390 (NH), 2931, 2852, 1616 (C=O), 1576, 1548, 1478, 1382, 1328, 1279, 1256, 1235, 1054, 1038, 889, 815, 714, 643, 616, 466, 408 cm^{-1} ; EIMS m/z (rel. int.) : 127 $[\text{M}]^+$ (5).

N-Butylformamide (**19**) : Liquid⁵³; yield 98%; FT-IR (neat) $\bar{\nu}$: 3412 (NH), 2955, 2921, 2851, 1640 (C=O), 1458, 1376, 1217, 1118, 1088, 771 cm^{-1} ; EIMS m/z (rel. int.) : 100 $[\text{M}-1]^+$ (2).

N-(2-Hydroxyethyl)formamide (**20**) : Liquid⁵⁴; yield 95%; FT-IR (neat) $\bar{\nu}$: 3551–2500, 1617 (C=O), 1378, 1345, 1071, 1017, 767, 473 cm^{-1} .

Piperidine-1-carbaldehyde (**21**) : Liquid⁵⁵; yield 98%; FT-IR (neat) $\bar{\nu}$: 2925, 2863, 1661 (C=O), 1443, 1399, 1364, 1272, 1232, 1112, 1069, 1006, 931, 856, 768, 667, 595 cm^{-1} .

Morpholine-4-carbaldehyde (**22**) : Liquid⁵⁶; yield 95%; FT-IR (neat) $\bar{\nu}$: 2974, 2925, 2863, 1658 (C=O), 1443, 1399, 1364, 1272, 1232, 1112, 1069, 1006, 931, 856, 768, 667, 595 cm^{-1} ; ¹H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) δ : 7.98 (1H, s, CHO), 3.62 (2H, t, J 4.8 Hz, CH_2O), 3.58 (2H, t, J 4.8 Hz, CH_2O), 3.49 (2H, t, J 4.8 Hz, CH_2N), 3.33 (2H, t, J 4.8 Hz, CH_2N); ¹³C NMR (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz) δ : 160.8 (C=O), 67.1 (C-O), 66.3 (C-O), 45.7 (C-N), 40.5 (C-N).

N-Methyl-N-phenylformamide (**23**) : Liquid⁵⁷; yield 94%; FT-IR (neat) $\bar{\nu}$: 3060, 2974, 2879, 2802, 1681 (C=O), 1596, 1497, 1413, 1350, 1313, 1270, 1116, 1029, 975, 820, 763, 697, 674, 536 cm^{-1} ; EIMS m/z (rel. int.) : 135 $[\text{M}]^+$ (100).

N-Ethyl-N-phenylformamide (**24**) : Liquid⁵⁷; yield 96%; FT-IR (neat) $\bar{\nu}$: 3064, 2976, 2935, 2874, 1679 (C=O), 1595, 1496, 1451, 1361, 1293, 1255, 1128, 1089, 1032, 815, 765, 698, 673, 549 cm^{-1} .

N-(Pyridin-2-yl)formamide (**25**) : Yield 97%; m.p. 67–69 °C (Lit. 69–70 °C)⁵⁸; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3363 (NH), 2786, 2700, 1689 (C=O), 1585, 1488, 1433, 1381, 1329, 1252, 1166, 1127, 978, 776, 683, 620, 553, 518, 441 cm^{-1} .

N-(Benzof[d]thiazol-2-yl)formamide (**26**) : Yield 98%;

m.p. 252–255 °C (Lit. 254–256 °C)⁵⁹; FT-IR (KBr) $\bar{\nu}$: 3411, 3292 (NH), 3119, 3083, 2827, 1628 (C=O), 1522, 1492, 1358, 1325, 1274, 1200, 1029, 882, 759, 694, 647, 515 cm^{-1} .

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